

Appendix 7 DEI Resources

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Table 1. DEI Resources

Content	Additional Information
<i>Books on Whiteness, Racism, and Antiracism</i>	
Title	Author
Me and White Supremacy	Layla F Saad
Waking Up White	Debby Irving
White Rage	Carol Anderson
Why I'm No Longer Talking to White People About Race	Renni Eddo-Lodge
How to be an Antiracist	Ibram X Kendi
So You Want to Talk About Race	Ijeoma Oluo
White Fragility	Robin DiAngelo
<i>Books on Systemic Racism</i>	
The Color of Law	Richard Rothstein
The Color of Money	Mehrsa Baradaran
The New Jim Crow	Michelle Alexander
Just Mercy	Bryan Stevenson
<i>Books on Systemic Racism in Medicine</i>	
Medical Apartheid: The Dark History of Medical Experimentation on Black Americans from Colonial Times to the Present	Harriet A. Washington
Black Man in a White Coat (A Doctor's Reflections on Race and Medicine)	Damon Tweedy
Dying of Whiteness	Johnathan Metz
The Immortal Life of Henrietta Lacks	Rebecca Skloot

LINKS

General

[Cultural Competence Education \(https://www.aamc.org/system/files/c/2/54338-culturalcomped.pdf\)](https://www.aamc.org/system/files/c/2/54338-culturalcomped.pdf)
[Identifying and Avoiding Bias in Research \(https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2917255/\)](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2917255/)
[Resources on inclusion in education \(https://en.unesco.org/themes/inclusion-in-education/resources\)](https://en.unesco.org/themes/inclusion-in-education/resources)

Anti-racism

[Anti-Racism Resource Guide \(https://med.emory.edu/about/diversity/anti-racism-guide.html\)](https://med.emory.edu/about/diversity/anti-racism-guide.html)
[Anti-Racism Resources \(https://www.med.upenn.edu/uphscovid19education/assets/user-](https://www.med.upenn.edu/uphscovid19education/assets/user-)
[Anti-Racism resources – Race & Equity Initiative \(https://www.washington.edu/raceequity/resources/anti-racism-](https://www.washington.edu/raceequity/resources/anti-racism-)
[Data Standards for the Identification and Monitoring of Systemic Racism \(https://www.ontario.ca/document/data-](https://www.ontario.ca/document/data-)
[Implicit Racial/Ethnic Bias Among Health Care Professionals and Its Influence on Health Care Outcomes: A The Physician's Role in Racial Equity \(https://www.bmc.org/healthcity/policy-and-industry/physicians-role-racial-equity\)](https://www.bmc.org/healthcity/policy-and-industry/physicians-role-racial-equity)
[White Privilege in a White Coat: How Racism Shaped my Medical Education](#)

Anti-Black Racism

[Anti-Black Racism Education Resource List \(https://www.nyu.edu/alumni/news-publications/nyu-connect-](https://www.nyu.edu/alumni/news-publications/nyu-connect-)
[Anti-Racism Resources: Educate Yourself \(https://www.projecthome.org/anti-racism-resources\)](https://www.projecthome.org/anti-racism-resources)

[Black Lives Matter – Anti Racism Resources \(https://library.ecu.edu/engagement/blm/\)](https://library.ecu.edu/engagement/blm/)

[Black Lives Matter: Anti-Racism Resources for Social Workers and Therapists](#)

Anti-Indigenous Bias

[Health Care Providers' Negative Implicit Attitudes and Stereotypes of American Indians](#)

[Native Americans – Bias Busters: Cultural competence guides](#)

[Unconscious Biases: Racial Microaggressions in American Indian Health Care](#)

LGBTQIA+

[GLAAD Media Reference Guide \(https://www.glaad.org/reference/\)](https://www.glaad.org/reference/)

[Guides & Brochures - LGBTQ Center \(https://lgbtq.wfu.edu/resources/guides-brochures/\)](https://lgbtq.wfu.edu/resources/guides-brochures/)

[Homophobia and the moral authority of medicine \(https://doi.org/10.1300/j082v27n03_14\)](https://doi.org/10.1300/j082v27n03_14)

[LGBTQ Resource List \(https://www.glaad.org/resourcelist\)](https://www.glaad.org/resourcelist)

Pronouns

[What Are Pronouns? Why Do They Matter? \(https://www.mypronouns.org/what-and-why\)](https://www.mypronouns.org/what-and-why)

[Pronoun Island \(https://pronoun.is/\)](https://pronoun.is/)

Transgender People

[Suggested Tables for Collection of Gender/Sex Information, Created by Clair Kronk for the Gender Harmony Project](#)

[Trans Bodies, Trans Selves: A Resource for the Transgender Community \(http://transbodies.com/\)](http://transbodies.com/)

[Transphobia rather than education predicts provider knowledge of transgender health care](#)